

DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

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The article focuses on specific features of agriculture and the role of entrepreneurship in it. Also, the opinions of scientists who conducted scientific research in the field of agricultural entrepreneurship were studied and analyzed. Current problems and prospects of agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan are presented. Proposals and recommendations on the solution of the shortage of specialists in the field of agriculture and the existing problems in entrepreneurship are given.

Key words: Agriculture, entrepreneurship, agro-business, technology, economy, product quality.

Introduction. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of the national economy, the development of small entrepreneurship in agricultural production, which reproduces its products on an industrial basis, is developing simultaneously with the implementation of market reforms.

In the process of transition to market relations, entrepreneurial forms play a decisive role in the development of employment of the population. Private initiative in entrepreneurship is a driving force in the current economic process. Development of entrepreneurship is one of the main directions of any market reform. One of the economic essence and important aspects of entrepreneurship is the constant growth of its share in the gross domestic product. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, 31 percent in 2000, 54.2 percent by 2021, and more than 82 percent of the population employed in the economy are their contribution. The republican and regional indicators of the share of small business and private business entities in the gross domestic product and the share of the population employed in the economy in small business entities are developing with a difference of 1.5-2.0 percent.

There is not a single economic activity that does not feel a practical need for it in modern social life. Entrepreneurship develops taking into account specific demographic and economic conditions in each country and some of its regions, and the development of the entrepreneurial direction is related to the practical tasks of our country's economy in a specific state.

One of the goals of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 is to create conditions for the organization of business activities and the formation of permanent sources of income, the share of the private sector in the GDP to 80% and the share of exports to 80% to 60% and to increase the income of peasants and farmers by at least 2 times through the intensive development of agriculture on a scientific basis, to increase the annual growth of agriculture to at least 5%.

Development of entrepreneurship, especially in the agricultural sector, is one of the important tasks of our country. Agriculture is one of the most important industries in the world. It can be said that agriculture not only provides food for all people but also keeps them busy. Its implementation depends on the joint activity of entrepreneurship and agriculture. This cooperation serves the stabilization of the economy and global economic development. Entrepreneurship in global economic development faces a number of challenges, challenges and obstacles due to the unique characteristics of agriculture and the risks associated with it. Therefore, it is necessary to form a highly effective, competitive business activity in agriculture.

The growth of the contribution of small and private business enterprises in the gross domestic product and the level of employment in developed and developing countries shows that the advantage of small business and private enterprises in the conditions of the market economy, their role and importance in ensuring the stability of the country is increasing. In particular, the majority of the population in the countries of the world is small operates in the business sector. For example, 80% of the population in China, 48% in Japan, 50% in the USA, and 78% in Uzbekistan are employed in small business. The share of small business in the economy is also high in the countries of the world, including 60% in China, 68% in Italy, 53% in Germany, 48% in Korea, 50% in the USA, 21% in Russia, and 56% in Uzbekistan. Business entities per 1000 inhabitants make up 57 units in the European Union, 90 units in the USA, 27.2 units in Russia [9], and 22 units in Uzbekistan.

According to statistics, in developed, economically stable countries, the difference between countries in the share of small business and private enterprises in the GDP is 5-10 percent, and in Uzbekistan, this indicator differs by 15-17 percent.

Table 1

The share of small business in the production of agricultural products in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Indicators	2000	2005	2010	2015	2021	2021 in 2000 year-on-year change, point
The area of agricultural crops, thousand hectares	3778,3	3647,5	3708,4	3694,2	3260,7	0,9
Production of agricultural products output, billion soum	1387,2	5978,3	30856,7	99604,6	302524,9	218,1
Production volume of agricultural products in small business and private enterprise, billion soums	1021	5019,7	29900,4	98198	299280	293,1
Production of agricultural products share of small business in output,%	73,6	84,0	96,9	98,6	98,9	1,3

Per thousand hectares of land coming agriculture products, billion soum	0 , 4	1,6	8,3	27,0	92,8	252,7
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There are 3,260.7 thousand hectares of cultivated land in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has decreased by 10% compared to 2000. However, the production volume of agricultural products in 2021 amounted to 302,524.9 billion soums, an increase of 218.1 points compared to 2000. The share of small business in the production of agricultural products was 98.2 percent, and the volume of production of agricultural products was 299,280.0 billion soums. Agricultural enterprises made 92.8 billion soums per thousand hectares and increased by 252.2 points compared to 2000. Although the volume of production of agricultural products is increasing, changes in the ownership patterns of rural the unemployment rate of the population is increasing. In recent years, as a result of lack of entrepreneurship skills among agricultural specialists, the influx of entrepreneurs from other sectors has increased. Over the years, the decline of specialists in this field has had a negative impact on agricultural entrepreneurship.

According to A.N. Asaul [1], entrepreneurship is a specific type of economic activity, the essence of which is to stimulate the demand of the society for the specific needs of its members through market exchange, and it is aimed at gaining competitive advantages by disrupting the market balance. Entrepreneurship in agriculture involves the participation of certain subjects and objects of entrepreneurial activity. I.V. According to Ukrainseva[2], economic entities are the entrepreneurs themselves who carry out economic activities and take full responsibility.

Russian magazine "Chief Director" [9] two main global problem areas admits:

1. the level of people in need of food and the backwardness of agrarian relations. In many developing countries, their own agriculture is unable to provide food for the population and meet their nutritional needs. That is why many are suffering from hunger. After all, although the volume of production increased, the number of hungry people was still the majority. According to the United Nations Population Fund as of January 1, 2021. Currently, the number of poor people in the world is about 1181.25 million people, which is about 15% of the total population. Considering that 60 percent of the world's population is in Asian countries, it means that these countries have a large number of people who cannot meet their basic needs. Also, in developed countries, there are 17.6 million (12.1%) poor people with an income below the subsistence minimum, including Russia.2. The number of poor in the European Union is 85 million (17%) people, in the United States of America 40 million. constitutes a person 3. In this regard, this problem is the first and most important.

2. Second world problem is related to agrarian relations. It appeared due to the difference in the development of agriculture in different countries. In some countries, the agricultural sector is advanced by adopting new high-efficiency technologies and growing methods. But in some countries, based on the remnants of the past, the forms of ownership and relations compatible with market relations have not been put on the right track. This gap creates difficulties in agricultural relations between the countries. This situation will not affect the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In developed and developing countries based on the market economy, small businesses and private enterprises are performing several main tasks. It has been equalizing the social costs of necessary structural changes in the economy by creating new jobs. It shows the need to develop small business and private entrepreneurship in the process of implementation of the market economy in Uzbekistan and to consistently study the experience of foreign countries in this regard.

Based on the above, it can be said that the economic policy aimed at building a democratic society conducted by the state and local authorities, a fully functioning market economy based on the priority of private ownership, should include the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in today's economic development strategy.

Small business has not only economic importance but also social importance, which can be expressed in the following:

- development of small entrepreneurship with jobs for the working population provides;
- increasing the material interest of the population engaged in production provides;
- small business development to fully meet the growing needs of the population provides;
- small entrepreneurship fulfills the potential of employable citizens allows to show and ensures the formation of middle-class owners in the society.

As a result of the economic reforms carried out in the agro-industry complex, business entities based on different ownership were formed, suitable for the market economy. Some property entities are being privatized and transformed into private-individual, private-collective business forms. In the field of production of agricultural products of the agro-industrial complex, first collective (company) farms, including farms and peasant farms, were established.

On the basis of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the concept of development of farms in 2004-2006", loss-making cooperative farms (except for specialized cooperative farms) were liquidated and turned into farms.

Ўзбекистон республикаси вазирлар маҳкамасининг 2019 йил 9 On the basis of January 14 Resolution No. 14 on additional measures to improve land reclamation of farms and other agricultural enterprises and effective use of agricultural land, the land of farms is optimized, and the sizes of plots of land of agricultural enterprises are determined as follows:

- ☐ minimum amount of land plots for cotton and grain agricultural enterprises - 100 hectares;
- ☐ the minimum amount of land plots of agricultural enterprises in the field of grain and vegetable growing - 20 hectares;
- ☐ the minimum amount of land plots for horticulture and viticulture enterprises - 10 hectares;
- ☐ The minimum size of the plots of vegetable and horticultural enterprises is 5 hectares.

In addition to the knowledge and experience of the entrepreneur, the entrepreneurial activity in the agricultural sector is influenced by the state policy and specifics of agriculture. Including, this situation is the basis for the formation of ownership in agriculture.

Conclusions and suggestions

In conclusion, it can be said that entrepreneurship, as an economic category, an important element of the market economy, has been taking its place in society since the Middle Ages until now. Although entrepreneurship is created through the movement and labor of people, it embodies a separate group of business people separated from labor resources. In the course of the development of entrepreneurship, people of this group mastered the features of organizing production, providing it with production resources, operating on the basis of risk, ensuring profit, and using innovative innovations. If we approach from this point of view, entrepreneurship is a production and service activity that includes the process of combining and mobilizing resources and managing them based on innovation and risk for the purpose of profit. Also in the agricultural sector

Even in the agro-industrial complex, entrepreneurship reflects private relations without changing its socio-economic essence. It ensures development in socio-economic connection. It is based on socio-economic, production relations with land, seasonality of agriculture, natural climatic conditions and mutual socio-economic relations of business entities in the agro-industrial complex.

Private individual and private collective entrepreneurship was formed in the agro-industrial complex on the basis of private and collective ownership. In the agro-industrial complex, private - sole entrepreneurship has developed in the following directions: farms in the field of agricultural products production, farming; in the field of service in cultural-household, trade, paid services; in the field of processing, small enterprises processing fruit and vegetables, fruit and milk, and individual business entities processing grain have developed. In the form of a private collective, some specialized joint-stock farms producing agricultural products, agro-firms, seed, fuel, fertilizer, water supply and technical service enterprises, and processing enterprises with a large technological base are formed.

In the research work, the following scientific recommendations aimed at the sustainable development of small entrepreneurship in the agro-industrial complex were developed:

The development of small entrepreneurship in the agro-industrial complex is mainly in two directions: the production of agricultural products and the production of the processing industry, and the service sector depends on their development. Therefore, it is desirable to organize cooperation in infrastructure directions in the material base of agricultural producers and processing enterprises.

☒ by increasing the attraction of foreign and local investments, it is necessary to establish compact enterprises equipped with modern equipment and high technologies for processing agricultural products. туманларидаги агрофирмалар маҳсулотларини экспорт салоҳиятини ошириш лозим. Бунда барча туманлардаги агрофирмалар иш фаолиятини қайта ташкил этиш, ишлаб чиқарилаётган маҳсулотлар сифатини жаҳон бозори талаблари даражасига етказиш бўйича чора-тадбирлар ишлаб чиқилиши зарур бўлади.

☒ it is necessary to eliminate imbalances between sectors and ensure balance between sectors. It is necessary to increase the share of small business activities in other sectors by ensuring that the total share of small business entities in agriculture is around 60 percent.

In the agro-industrial complex, mainly farms and peasant farms operate as subjects producing agricultural products. In peasant farms, the production of livestock products is more important than the production of agricultural products. Farms occupy a leading position in the production of agricultural products, while the production of livestock products is developing informally only in family contexts. This shows that the activities of both economic

entities have a tendency to develop in dependence on each other, and this strengthens the penetration of the processing industry.

In developing the scope of this activity, first of all, to formalize the production of livestock products on farms and to create the possibility of growing fodder on land. It is also necessary to establish sales outlets for fodder and other products produced by processing agricultural products. Secondly, it is necessary to take measures to transfer agricultural holdings from the informal sector to the formal sector and regulate contractual relations in them

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